

A self-supervised deep learning approach to synthesize weighted images and T1, T2, and PD parametric maps based on MR physics priors

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Synopsis: Synthetic MRI is gaining popularity due to its ability to generate realistic MR images. However, T1, T2, and PD maps are rarely used despite they provide the information needed to synthesize any image modality by applying the appropriate theoretical equations derived from MR physics or through involved simulation procedures. In this work we propose an extension of an state-of-the-art standard CNN to a self-supervised CNN by including MR physics priors to tackle confounding factors not considered in the equations, while bypassing the need of costly simulations. Our approach yields both realistic maps and weighted images from real data.

Main Findings:

- A self-supervised deep learning approach to compute T1, T2, and PD parametric maps from clinical routine sequences.
- Any realistic weighted images can be synthesized from the parametric maps.
- The proposed self-supervised CNN achieves significant improvements in most synthesized modalities.

Purpose: Synthetic MRI has gained popularity due to its ability to generate realistic MR images. The synthesized images may improve diagnostic reliability without extra acquisition time and facilitate physicians training¹. Various synthetic MRI approaches²⁻⁴ have been proposed that learn a rigid mapping between different image modalities, e.g., the synthesis of T1-weighted (T1w) images from T2-weighted (T2w) images⁴. However, these approaches do not take advantage of the quantitative T1, T2, and PD parametric maps which would ideally allow for the synthesis of any image modality by applying the appropriate theoretical equations derived from MR physics or performing costly simulations. Despite their potential, these parametric maps are rarely obtained in the clinical routine because each map needs the application of specific and lengthy relaxometry sequences^{5,6}. To overcome this limitation, Ref⁷ proposed a method to compute T1, T2, and PD maps from a T1w and a T2w using a convolutional-neural-network (CNN) exclusively trained with synthetic data. However, additional sequence parameters and confounding factors were not considered in the theoretical equations⁸. Thus, the synthesis through these equations and maps might affect accuracy, causing differences between the synthesized and acquired images. Many aspects could be tackled with detailed and costly simulations, but non-ideal conditions would still remain⁸. Thus, we propose an extension of the previous standard CNN to a self-supervised CNN by including MR physics priors, and re-training it with few acquired weighted images. This way, we tailor these parametric maps to be used with the theoretical equations, counteracting the effects not considered and leveraging the synthesis of realistic weighted images.

Methods:

Acquisitions and preprocessing: Eight patients, suspected of Alzheimer's disease, were recruited for *Brain MRI* protocol with IRB approval and informed written consent. *Brain MRI* was acquired with a 32-channel head coil on a 3T scanner (Philips, Best, The Netherlands). Table 1 gives details of the protocol and the five image modalities acquired. Subsequently, all image modalities were affine-registered to the FLAIR using FSL⁹. All images were then skull-stripped and cropped to the dimension of the network's input layer⁷ (240x176 pixels). Finally, for optimization purposes we normalized the weighted images by dividing each of them by its average intensity without considering the background.

CNN training: Starting from the pre-trained encoder/decoder CNN of Ref⁷ to synthesize T1, T2, and PD maps from a T1w and a T2w image, we converted this CNN⁷ into a self-supervised CNN by adding lambda layers with fixed weights after the decoders outputs (Figure 1a). Each of these layers implements a different theoretical equation corresponding to a particular sequence¹⁰ that describes MR intensity as a function of scanner parameters together with the T1, T2, and PD maps. As a result, the self-supervised CNN is able to synthesize any desired weighted image. In this case, a T1w and a T2w image (eight minutes acquisition) were input to the CNN, and five output lambda layers for the synthesis of a T1w, T2w, PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR were considered. Corresponding equations and parameters are shown in Figure 1b and Table 1, respectively. The loss function was computed as the mean absolute error between the synthesized and their corresponding acquired weighted images. The proposed self-supervised CNN was then re-trained using Adam optimizer with a batch size of 8 images. From the eight patients, we used 4 for re-training, two for validation with early-stopping to avoid overfitting, and two for testing.

CNN testing: For the T1w and T2w images of the two test patients, the self-supervised CNN provided the computed T1, T2, and PD maps and the synthesized T1w, T2w, PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR images (see Figure 1a). The following metrics were used to evaluate the synthesis quality of the weighted outputs: mean-squared-error³, structural-similarity-index³, and peak signal-to-noise ratio³.

Results: Figure 2 shows a representative slice of the T1, T2, and PD maps computed for each of the test patients. Figure 3 shows a representative slice of the synthesized and their corresponding acquired weighted images for each of the test patients. Finally, boxplots of the evaluation metrics are shown in Figure 4.

Discussion: These preliminary results show the potential of the proposed self-supervised deep learning approach to compute T1, T2, and PD parametric maps within expected ranges for 3T scanners and to synthesize any weighted image by means of

MR physics priors included in the CNN. The self-supervised CNN achieves higher metrics than the standard CNN⁷, particularly for the PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR images, with statistical significant differences in most image modalities. Further, the metrics obtained are comparable with those obtained by state-of-the-art synthetic MRI methods^{2-4,7} to generate a synthetic image from one or more inputs. Note that, using the proposed approach, other modalities unseen by the network could be synthesized from the computed parametric maps. Nevertheless, this work has several limitations, we present a proof of concept with limited training and testing data, so further validation with larger databases is still required.

Conclusion: We proposed an approach for the synthesis of realistic weighted images based on the computation of T1, T2, and PD parametric maps which only needs two input images. Results suggest its utility for quantitative MRI in clinical viable times as well as its applications to synthesize any image modality.

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	T1w (MP-GRE)	T2*w (GRE)	FLAIR (IR-TSE)	PDw/T2w (TSE)
TE (ms)	3	20	100	30/85
TR (ms)	6.44	746.99	11000	4000
TI (ms)	900	-	2800	-
α ($^{\circ}$)	10	20	-	-
ETL	192	1	12	10
SENSE	1.8/1/1.2	2	2	2
NSA	1	1	1	1
# Slices	170 (sagittal)	27 (axial)	27 (axial)	50 (axial)
Thickness (mm)	1.2	5	5	3
Resolution (mm ²)	1.25 \times 1.25	0.94 \times 1.25	0.94 \times 1.25	1.02 \times 1.36
FOV (mm)	240 \times 240	240 \times 240	240 \times 240	260 \times 195
Scan time (min)	\sim 4:00	2:30 - 4:00	2:30 - 4:30	2:30 - 4:30

Table 1: Acquisitions parameters of the *Brain MRI* protocol. Each protocol session was composed of four sequences and a total of five image modalities, namely, a 3D T1-weighted (T1w) magnetic preparation gradient echo (MP-GRE) sequence, a

T2*-weighted (T2*w) GRE sequence, a T2-weighted fluid attenuation inversion recovery (FLAIR) sequence, and a PD/T2-weighted (PDw/T2w) turbo spin echo (TSE) multi echo sequence.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed approach. a) Pipeline for training and testing the self-supervised convolutional-neural-network (CNN). b) Equations of the lambda layers used to synthesize the T1w, T2w, PDw, T2*w and FLAIR images from the previously computed parametric maps with sequence parameters of Table 1. $m(\mathbf{x})$ is the signal intensity of the corresponding

weighted image at pixel x . Note that the CNN is pre-trained exclusively with synthetic data, as described in Ref⁷, and that PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR images are only used to compute the loss function and are not input to the CNN.

Figure 2: A representative axial slice of the T1, T2, and PD parametric maps computed for each test patient. a) T1w and T2w acquired weighted images input to the self-supervised CNN. b), c), and d) computed T1, T2, and PD maps of the same slice, respectively. T1 and T2 values are given in seconds (s). The computed parametric maps are visually realistic with values within

the literature for 3T scanners and also capture most of the structural information. Note that no outliers appear in the CSF of the T1 maps.

Figure 3: A representative axial slice of the synthesized and the corresponding acquired weighted images for each test patient. a-e) T1w, T2w, PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR images synthesized by the self-supervised CNN. f-j) Corresponding images synthesized by the standard CNN. k-o) Corresponding acquired images. The self-supervised CNN achieves better structural information and contrast than the standard CNN obtaining higher quality synthesis. Specifically, for the PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR which had the lowest quality synthesis in the standard CNN. See the CSF of the PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR.

Figure 4: Boxplots of the slice-wise metrics used to assess the synthesis quality of the weighted images synthesized by the standard CNN and the self-supervised CNN. The metrics were calculated slice-wise between the synthesized and the acquired weighted images. A Wilcoxon signed rank test was performed for each metric and each modality. Significant P-values ($P < 0.05$) are shown in bold. Statistical significant differences are found for most image modalities being the improvement of the self-supervised CNN higher for PDw, T2*w, and FLAIR images.